

ICCOB OA 012

**Evaluation of Phytoremediation Potential of selected Marigold plant
species for removal of Heavy Metals from Soil**

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Environmental contamination of soil by heavy metals is a serious problem worldwide due to their toxicity, immutable nature, accumulation in food chain and continued persistence in ecosystem. Conventional technologies involve physical displacement or chemical replacement, generating yet another problem of toxic sludge. Phytoremediation is a cost-effective, non-intrusive, and aesthetically pleasing technology in which herbaceous plants and trees are used to remediate and remove pollutants from soils. Applying ornamental plants for phytoremediation could be useful, for example in contaminated urban areas, because these plants can also improve the environment by their decorative value. In this study three species of Marigold plants *Calendula officinalis*, *Tagetes erecta*, *Tagetes patula* were assessed for their heavy metal accumulation potential. Pot experiments were conducted for various concentrations of heavy metals (ranging from 10 mg/kg to 200 mg/kg). The plant uptake of the heavy metals was analyzed after a 12-week growing period and was determined by analyzing residual heavy metal concentrations in aerial and subterranean parts of the plant by atomic absorption spectrophotometry (AAS). A comparison has been made for the bioaccumulation factor (BAF), translocation factor of all these plant for Chromium, Lead, Cadmium and Arsenic. According to the obtained outcome all these three species of marigold found to be efficient bioaccumulator of Chromium, Lead, Cadmium and Arsenic from contaminated soils, since it can accumulate these heavy metals in its tissues, and plant biomass do not decrease due to excessive amounts of heavy metals. Pot marigold *Calendula officinalis* can accumulate Chromium, Lead, Cadmium and Arsenic however it is more sensitive to the toxicity of heavy metals than *Tagetes erecta* and *Tagetes patula*. All these three species of marigold plants can be used in an environment-friendly approach for treating heavy metal contaminated landfills developed using heavy metal contaminated riverbed sediments.

Keywords: Phytoextraction, Heavy Metal, Tagetes erecta, Tagetes patula Phytoremediation, Calendula officinalis